

Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center

2023-24 Seed Grant Program Final Report

Exploring geomorphology of active offshore faults in Cascadia and building pathways to STEM engagement at the Quileute Tribal School

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Did you accomplish what you set out with this project?

Overall, we accomplished what we set out to do for both Phase 1 and Phase 2 of this project. The CRESCENT Seed grant enabled us to spark new interdisciplinary research collaborations, train early career researchers, and develop new methodologies in submarine geomorphology to understand splay fault activity at the Cascadia accretionary wedge. It also allowed for the continuation and growth of Culture and Science Exchange (CASE) programs with the Quileute and Makah Tribes. Our work in K-12 education of tribal youth is crucial towards building trust and deepening partnerships with outer coast tribes in Washington that are affected by Cascadia subduction zone hazards.

Phase 1: Geomorphic analysis of offshore faults in Cascadia across space and time using high-resolution bathymetry

Two undergraduate students (Elisabeth Olson and Alyssa Iverson), mentored by UW graduate student (Madeleine Lucas), completed a full cross-channel (**Figure 1**) and along-channel (**Figure 2**) geomorphic characterization of the Astoria submarine channel using ArcGIS Pro and MATLAB Topotoolbox. Their analysis revealed channel knickpoints linked to both active and inactive fault zones crossing the Astoria channel. Knickpoints associated with active faults were co-located with the trace of the fault, whereas knickpoints associated with inactive faults were located up-channel of the fault trace. Major knickzones were also identified that we hypothesize may be linked to either deeper fault uplift or large submarine landslides.

Through this project, both students learned and applied practical research skills in GIS, coding, and geomorphic analysis of submarine landscapes. Under the mentorship of Lucas, Olson and Iverson regularly attended UW Geoscapes (Geomorphology) and FaSST (Structure/Geophysics) Lab Group meetings to present updates and get feedback on their projects. Towards her work on this project, Iverson was awarded the highly competitive and prestigious UW Mary Gates Research Scholarship.

Figure 1 Example of cross-channel analysis of the Astoria submarine channel in ArcGIS Pro.

Figure 2 Example of along-channel analysis of the Astoria submarine channel in MATLAB TopoToolbox.

Lucas achieved the proposed project goals in her joint geomorphic and structural characterization of the Albatross strike-slip fault zone. Using USGS 30-m bathymetry and our newly compiled 15-m multibeam bathymetry dataset, Lucas analyzed the geomorphic expression of the active fault system and identified piercing points where the fault offsets older seafloor features (Figure 3). In addition, she utilized recently acquired high-resolution seismic reflection datasets in addition to deeper CASIE21 and USGS sparker seismic imaging to further characterize cross-cutting relationships between older and younger subsurface structures and to identify locations where inferred-Holocene sediments are deformed (Figure 4). Lucas presented her preliminary findings for this project at AGU24 and will be presenting her final analysis at 11th IAG International Conference on Geomorphology in New Zealand. A manuscript detailing her findings is complete and will be submitted to the *G-cubed* shortly.

Figure 3 Hillshaded 15-meter multibeam bathymetry with interpreted structural morphology of the Albatross Fault System.

Figure 4 Sparker and SBP seismic profiles capturing subsurface structure of the Albatross Fault system

Key Project Outcomes from Phase 1:

- Lucas oral presentation at AGU24 entitled “Active strike-slip fault system accommodates oblique convergence at the Cascadia Subduction Zone”
- Iverson oral presentation at the UW Undergraduate Research Symposium entitled “Linking Submarine Channel Morphology to Tectonic Processes at the Cascadia Subduction Zone”
- Elizabeth Olson oral presentation at the 2025 ESS Research Gala
- Fault outputs from Lucas’ project on strike-slip faulting offshore Oregon are currently being incorporated into CRESCENT’s Community Faults Model (CFM).
- All fault mapping produced by this project will be released in the next version of the USGS Quaternary Faults database in collaboration with the USGS Pacific Coastal and Marine Science Center (Fall 2025).
- Three manuscripts stemming from the Seed grant are in preparation for submission:
 - Iverson et al. (in prep for *JGR Earth Surface*) “Linking Astoria Submarine Channel Morphology to Tectonic Processes at Cascadia Subduction Zone”.

- Lucas et al. (in prep for *JGR Earth Surface*) “Morphologic Signature of Active Splay Faulting in Cascadia’s Submarine Channels”
- Lucas et al. (in prep for *G-Cubed*) “Distributed Shearing Accommodates Oblique Convergence at the Cascadia Subduction Zone”
- Seed grant work contributed to successful funding of NEHRP grant application “Evaluating earthquake and tsunami hazard from offshore margin-parallel strike-slip faults, Cascadia subduction zone”.
- Iverson was awarded the UW Mary Gates Research Scholarship.

Future Work:

- Iverson poster presentation at AGU25 entitled “Linking Submarine Channel Morphology to Tectonic Processes at the Cascadia Subduction Zone”
- Lucas oral presentation entitled “Morphologic signature of active splay faulting in Cascadia’s submarine channels” at 11th IAG International Conference on Geomorphology in New Zealand

Phase 2: Exchanging culture and science at the Quileute Tribal School

For Phase 2, we accomplished everything and more than what was originally planned with the founding of the Cascadia Culture and geoScience Exchange (CCASE) program and expansion of CASE programming to the Neah Bay High School (Makah CASE). This was enabled by additional matched support from the CRESCENT High School STEM Program. Each year, our K-12 educational programming for the CCASE program evolves and adapts to the needs and desires of our high school students and their teachers throughout the academic year. However, this does not change the core outcomes of our program to engage tribal youth in geoscience.

For Phase 2, we developed a 5-day place-based and culturally-informed geomorphology curriculum that our team of UW students taught over spring break. Our curriculum highlights synergies between indigenous and western science. We taught our students that *Science is Storytelling* through a guided *Indigenous Science Toolbox* developed primarily by Quileute CASE team member René Castillo. Our teaching focused on understanding how local rivers around La Push work, change, and impact the Quileute community. A key topic we focused on was erosion caused by the Quillayute River. During our field trip, we invited local scientist Sierra Hemmig from Quileute Natural Resources to show us sites where erosion threatens tribal lands and important cultural resources. Our students also got the opportunity to see how the tribe was implementing log jams and other nature-based solutions to prevent further erosion with Jill Silver from the 10,000 Years Institute.

From our [mentorship](#) interviews with Quileute CASE high school interns Donald, Kaleb, and Olivia, we learned that the students were interested in gaining fieldwork experience. Based on this, we modified their high school internship project to be a field experience to track coastal erosion and retreat at Rialto Beach by monitoring the location of prominent coastal trees with respect to the first wave cut beach terrace in partnership with Elizabeth Davis. We spent two days in the field with high school interns to help the students learn about how to make observations in the field and document their observations in their notebooks (Figure 5). The students will be returning to measure the location of the trees every six months. In 2025-26, the students will be designing a poster presentation to report their findings to the local community.

Figure 5 QTS High School internship students Ethen and Donald measure the distance of trees to the first coastal terrace at Rialto Beach.

For our cultural exchange, the UW team was invited to make elk hide drums with QTS culture teacher Alexis Ward. Our drums were blessed at the Quileute drum group where the team had the opportunity to play traditional songs with the group (Figure 6). Cultural exchange through our program provides a unique opportunity for UW students undergraduate and graduate students to learn about the indigenous culture of the Quileute Tribe. Additionally, for our cultural visit in spring quarter, we were invited to join Quileute Welcoming the Whales Ceremony at First Beach in La Push. During spring break, we watched our high school students prepare for this ceremony every day, so to be there and support them during the ceremony was a very important way to wrap up the 2024-2025 CASE program in a good way.

Figure 6 Quileute CASE team with the Quileute drum group.

[From February 21-22, 2025, the Quileute CASE program hosted the Quileute high school at UW campus for a 2-day visit.](#) The high schoolers were led on a tour around campus, which included visits to the Burke Museum, the PNSN Seismolab, the UW Planetarium, and the Oceanography Puget Sound Table. We ended the day with dinner in Mary Gates Hall catered by the Off the Rez Cafe. The next day, the Riverways Guides, made up of indigenous undergraduates at UW, led a college access workshop for the students that guided them how to navigate the process of applying to college.

In its first year, the CASE-Makah program accomplished its goals of expanding the CASE programming to an additional school, enhancing coastal resilience, and embarking on a relationship with the Makah Tribe and Neah Bay High School. By adapting the CASE-Quileute model to Neah Bay, we successfully implemented the CCASE program and were invited to return and continue building trust with the Neah Bay community in 2025-2026.

Throughout the year at Neah Bay High School, we developed a week-long geohazards curriculum that we then taught during UW's spring break through Riverways STEM ASB program. Hands-on lessons integrated geoscience and indigenous knowledge, with local field trips and guest lectures from Elders providing vital place-based learning (GEI3). Our curriculum focused on Cascadia subduction zone earthquakes, tsunamis, and landslides. Specifically, our lessons focused on evidence for Cascadia subduction zone earthquakes (including paleoseismology findings, indigenous oral histories, etc.), earthquake engineering, tsunami generation and hazards, and landsliding hazards. We also organized a field trip to the local Makah Cultural and Research Center Museum, where artifacts that were recovered from a pre-historic landslide at an ancient Makah village preserved countless cultural artifacts.

Key Project Outcomes from Phase 2:

- Lucas was invited to give a long-format presentation of the CCASE program at Hatfield Marine Science Center Research Seminar on January 30, 2025. [\[link\]](#)
- Grossman and Lucas co-presented a talk on the CCASE program at the CRESCENT Annual Meeting (October 29, 2025).
- Grossman and Lucas co-presented a talk on the CCASE program the CoPes Hub Navigating Coastal Hazards 2 Workshop (February, 2025).
- Lucas presented on the CCASE program at the North Pacific Marine Resources Committee Meeting on March 19, 2025.
- Grossman and Lucas worked with GEI Program Manager Shannon Fasola to develop and publish the CCASE webpage [\[link\]](#) on the CRESCENT website. Individual subpages and blogs are regularly updated for Quileute [\[link\]](#) and Makah [\[link\]](#) CASE programs.
- CRESCENT GEI Coordinator Shannon Fasola joined us for both Quileute and Makah CASE over spring break, providing first-hand, in-person experience to a CRESCENT staff member into how CCASE programs function and engage tribal partners.
- Rene Castillo is preparing to publish the "Indigenous Science Toolbox" and "Science is Storytelling" curriculum.

Future Work:

- Grossman will be presenting on the CCASE program at AGU 2025 entitled "Cascadia Culture And geoScience Exchange (CCASE): Building Community Resilience to Cascadia Geohazards and Fostering STEM Identities of Indigenous Youth"
- 2024-2025 Seed project led to development and current implementation of 2025-2026 Seed project.
- The success of CCASE programs supported by CRESCENT Seed Grants has provided a strong foundation to apply for larger grant opportunities to support the continuation of CCASE and expansion to additional schools.